

EXPERT VALIDATION OF ENGAGEMENT BALANCE ELEMENTS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF WORK LIFE BALANCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN MALAYSIA

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 13 Dec 2023 Revised: 2 Jan 2024 Accepted: 20 Jan 2024 Published: 1 Feb 2024</p>	<p>Teacher's work-life balance is an important element that is getting the attention of today's society. The importance of life work cannot be achieved without the balance of teachers' engagement in their work and life. Therefore, this study was carried out to see the views and agreement of experts on the balance of engagement in the work management instrument of secondary school teachers' lives in Malaysia. Quantitative research is used through the distribution of Fuzzy Delphi Method (FDM) questionnaire instruments given to 9 experts. This study has set criteria for experts, namely lecturers and teachers who have served more than 5 years in teaching, learning and school management. All data collected was analyzed using FDM. The findings of the study show that all items in the balance of engagement meet the conditions, that is, the threshold value (<i>d construct</i>) is less than 0.2 and the percentage of expert agreement exceeds 75%. Therefore, the work-life balance management model for secondary school teachers in Malaysia needs to be included with all the items contained in the engagement balance element based on expert agreement.</p>
<p>Keywords: Work-Life Balance Engagement Balance Secondary School Teachers</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS</p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Work life balance is a process of managing work and family life towards achieving individual and organizational goals (Adebayo et al., 2020). Work-life balance can also be defined as achieving a satisfying experience in all domains of life (Aremu & Abogunrin, 2018). Therefore, the statement above concludes that the balance of individual demands is the same between work and life. Kirchmeyer (2000) states that to achieve satisfaction in all domains of life, individuals need existing personal resources such as energy, time and commitment to be well distributed. Thus, as an employee, teachers give their full energy, time and commitment in achieving a work-life balance through a balance of engagement.

Engagement balance is one of the three important elements that are at the core of managing work-life balance (Greenhaus et al., 2003). Therefore, it is the responsibility of all parties, whether teachers or school leaders, to try to balance psychological demands during work or outside work hours. As an important asset that contributes to the building of the nation, teachers play a role as implementers to achieve the objectives set by the government. Teacher readiness and commitment is an important aspect in determining success or failure in the implementation of an effective educational plan (Mehat et al., 2021). Because teachers play a role as implementers that influence the learning process and student decisions, then teachers should improve their performance (Gooding, 2018). Absolutely family-friendly policies and cultures are an important component in creating a healthy work environment and are positively related to work outcomes for employees and public organizations (Feeney & Stritch, 2019). As a result, employees who are teachers will be more committed, motivated and productive in the implementation of work and contribute to a positive impact on their organization (Thevanes & Mangaleswaran, 2018). However, the study found that the demands and conflicts of family work often burden women who work as teachers because they have to do two things simultaneously. They need to ensure that all aspects and affairs in the household are completed perfectly (Mohamad et al., 2020). The role of educators and teaching practices in management institutions has been affected by the rapidly developing education system in the new era (Kim, 2019 & Ha, 2020). As a result, teachers find it difficult to adapt to changes and challenges in the education system which can also contribute to stress and emotional disturbances (Majid & Surat, 2021). Furthermore, burden on teachers is increasing according to the changes in standards made by the ministry. Too much workload also puts pressure on teachers. Work pressure can lead to low morale, reduced effectiveness, high absenteeism, high stress and sometimes can cause 'burnout' and reduce commitment to the profession (Mehat et al., 2021). The emotional stress and disturbance of the teacher's feelings will have an impact on productivity and subsequently will also have an impact on the physical and psychological well-being of the teacher (Klai & Bahrin, 2020). Dhavala et.al (2019) in his study stated that women are more often exposed to conflict when compared to men. This is based on the fact that women will often put more effort into fulfilling the second shift (after managing the household). The effects of conflict can inhibit the level of well-being of female teachers in particular (Mehat et al., 2021). As a result, teachers will not be able to balance their work and life while neglecting the balance of engagement in work or after work hours. Thus, the balance of teachers' engagement in their careers and after work has an impact on the management of their work life.

LITERATURE REVIEW

WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Work life balance is a term that refers to an individual who balances work with personal life in one role, which ultimately helps success in balancing both (Fisher et al., 2009). Greenhaus (2013) said that individuals who have a work-life balance will have less burden. The opinion is based on the individual having an easier time allocation to complete the task. Schermerhorn (2012) stated that work-life balance is a broad concept covering the right choice of priorities between career and ambition as well as individual 'life' such as recreation, family, health, hobbies and spiritual development. In fact, spiritual elements in the workplace are recommended as an important medium to improve work life balance and employee well-being (Garg, 2017). Through the opinion, the researcher concluded that the work-life balance of teachers has a positive impact on the continuity of their careers and lives.

The positive impact related to the teacher's work-life balance is an increase in job satisfaction, a high job security, a reduction in the level of work stress as well as an increase in the physical and mental health of teachers (Riffay, 2019). The study also found that the effect of work-life balance is that individuals are less depressed than individuals who do not have a level of work-life balance (Rohmawati & Izzati, 2021). Individuals who have a work-life balance are able to carry out their roles in life smoothly. The study found that teachers who practice a family lifestyle have more work-life balance than teachers who practice a nuclear family lifestyle (Anbalagan, 2022). Apart from that, the effect of good work balance management is able to increase the individual's work spirit to the best level. The spirit of working at the best level is able to produce a positive organizational culture and increase productivity in work (Mangaharti & Noviati, 2019).

ENGAGEMENT BALANCE

Greenhaus, Collins and Shaw (2003) have outlined three main elements that make up work-life balance, namely time balance, engagement balance and satisfaction balance in their family and work roles. Engagement balance refers to the employee's psychological engagement with work and outside of work hours. The psychological engagement of employees in the career refers to the process of improving the level and performance of work. While the psychological engagement of employees outside of working hours refers to interpersonal relationships that involve emotions. Engagement balance has a positive effect on improving work life balance.

Individuals who have a work life balance are able to meet their own time needs to balance their life and work. As a result, the individual produces a good increase in subjective well-being. Subjective well-being will be obtained when their life goals are achieved (Martadinata et al., 2020). A study from Allam and Shaik (2020) asserted that work-life balance and well-being are sources of quality of life among academic staff in Saudi Arabia. A direct positive effect of engagement balance is increased job satisfaction (Riffay, 2019). In addition to that, teacher work productivity also increases (Pratama et al., 2022) along with an increase in moral value in the task (Rahmayani, 2021). In fact, Lee et al. (2019) suggested the importance of employees to work more effectively through increased teamwork. Apart from that, his opinion that leaders play a role in organizations that lead teams to achieve work life balance. Indirectly, the balance of engagement makes the individual's quality of life better (Mohammadi & Karupiah, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Number And Criteria of Experts

The use of the Fuzzy Delphi technique requires sufficient FDM samples. The number of samples between 8 and 12 is sufficient if the sample is homogeneous (Cavalli-Sforza, 1984). Expert samples can also be selected between 7 to 12 people (Philip, 2000). Thus, the number of experts involved in this study total 9 people. All selected experts have more than 5 years of service experience directly involved in teaching, learning and educational management (Berliner, 2004) and are able to answer all research questions.

Expert Questionnaire

This study uses a questionnaire using the Fuzzy Delphi Method (FDM) as an instrument to obtain quantitative data. The data was used to see the need for the element of engagement balance for the design phase of the work life management model for secondary school teachers in Malaysia. In order to meet the criteria and conditions for the use of the Fuzzy Delphi technique, the findings of the questionnaire were generated using mathematical formulas to obtain expert agreement. The researcher developed the questionnaire through the literature highlights related to the element of engagement balance. All the data of this study was collected using a questionnaire that has two parts as contained in Table 1:

Table 1. Questionnaire Section

Element	Number of items	Items
Engagement Balance	1	prepare lesson plan before starting the teaching and learning session according to the student's current level
	2	provide teaching aids before starting the teaching and learning session according to the students' current level
	3	manage teaching and learning according to the set timetable
	4	provide teaching reflection after the end of the teaching and learning session
	5	prepare a set of test/exam questions according to the current exam calendar
	6	prepare a set of test/exam schemes according to the current examination calendar according to the level that has been determined
	7	prepare test/exam sessions according to the time in the exam calendar and current exam instructions
	8	mark the exam answers according to the scheme provided
	9	key-in the exam scores for analysis and record purposes
	10	planning matters related to the operation of student affairs at school
	11	managing matters related to the operation of student affairs at the school
	12	identify and resolve issues related to student welfare at school
	13	supervise the special rooms of student affairs in the school according to the set portfolio
	14	managing activities that increase the school's level of achievement in the fields of cheerfulness, hygiene, health and safety according to the set portfolio
Engagement Balance	15	documenting student affairs activities at school according to the set portfolio
	16	plan extracurricular activities according to the school calendar given
	17	carry out co-curricular activities according to the school calendar according to the given school calendar
	18	planning activities that increase the level of school achievement in the extracurricular field
	19	supervise the special rooms of the school curriculum
	20	documenting school extracurricular activities
	21	attend a professional development program related to co-curriculum
	22	attend a continuous professional development program (CPD) to improve work competence
	23	record the presence of co-curricular professionalism development programs in the SPLKPM System
	24	master the skills of creating the latest educational technology and innovation
	25	master the skills of developing the latest educational technology and innovation
	26	master the skills of applying the latest educational technology and innovation
	27	master the latest educational digital literacy skills
	28	master the handling of the latest educational digital teaching aids
	29	master the culture of online working
	30	improve teamwork skills in school
	31	improve problem-solving skills involving tasks at school
32	improve decision-making skills involving tasks at school	
33	improve critical thinking skills in developing self-capacity at school	
34	rest after finishing in managing things related to work at school	
35	engage in sport activities to maintain personal fitness	

36	perform worship activities according to their respective religious beliefs
37	socialize with the communities where they live
38	managing the household with their partner at home
39	managing children's education with spouse at home

Validity And Reliability of Questionnaire Items

In determining the validity and reliability of the implementation of the Fuzzy Delphi technique, the researcher determines and organizes all the items found through the literature related to the element of engagement balance. All the items are provided in a schedule that can be understood by the expert panel. After that, the researcher submitted the questionnaire to the expert. The experts agree to give their contribution in conveying ideas, criticisms or improving the items that have been set. Confirmation of the review is carried out by experts through the form given after being satisfied with the questionnaire.

Data Analysis Procedures

There are several steps that need to be followed in order for this study using the Fuzzy Delphi Technique to be considered an empirical study. The steps are as follows :

Step 1 : Suppose that expert A is invited to determine the importance of the evaluation criteria for the variables to be measured using linguistic variables.

Step 2 : Convert to all linguistic variables into Fuzzy triangular numbering (triangular Fuzzy numbers). Suppose the fuzzy number r_{ij} is a variable for each criterion for expert K for $i : 1, \dots, m, j=1, \dots, n, k=1, \dots, k$ dan $r_{ij} = 1/K (r_{ij}^1 \pm r_{ij}^2 \pm r_{ij}^k)$

Table 2 shows the Fuzzy scale that includes linguistic variables showing for 5 scales in the Fuzzy Delphi Method :

Table 2 . Fuzzy Scale

Linguistic Variables	Fuzzy Scale
Very strong disagree	(0.0, 0.0, 0.1)
Strongly disagree	(0.0, 0.1, 0.3)
Disagree	(0.1, 0.3, 0.5)
Moderate agree	(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)
Agree	(0.5, 0.7, 0.9)
Strongly agree	(0.7, 0.9, 1.0)
Very strong agree	(0.9, 1.0, 1.0)

Step 3 : For each expert, use the vertex method to calculate the distance between the average ridges. (Chen, 2000). The distance between two Fuzzy numbers $m = (m_1, m_2, m_3)$ and $n = (n_1, n_2, n_3)$ is calculated using the formula:

$$d(\bar{m}, \bar{n}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} [(m_1 - n_1)^2 + (m_2 - n_2)^2 + (m_3 - n_3)^2]}$$

Step 4 : According to Cheng and Lin (2002), if the distance between the average and expert evaluation data is less than the threshold value of 0.2, then all the experts are considered to have reached a consensus. Also, among $m \times n$ experts, if the percentage of reaching group consensus is more than 75% (Chu & Hwang, 2008;

Murry & Hammons, 1995), then go to step 5. If contrary data is found, a second round of the Fuzzy Delphi Method must be performed or the item is discarded.

Step 5 : Fuzzy evaluation aggregate with :

$$\bar{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_1 \\ \bar{A}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \bar{A}_m \end{bmatrix}$$

$i = 1, \dots, m$

Step 6 : For each alternative option, Fuzzy evaluation $A_i = (m_1, m_2, m_3)$ in defuzzication with $A : 1/3 * (m_1 + m_2 + m_3)$. Alternative order of ranking options can be determined according to the value a_i .

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 3 displays the items of the Elements of Engagement Balance which include the items of essential academic duties, student affairs, co-curriculum, professionalism, personal and family responsibility, community relations, physical needs and religious appreciation.

Table 3. The final findings of the main items for the Elements of Engagement Balance that have been agreed upon and recommended by experts

Number of items	ELEMENTS OF ENGAGEMENT BALANCE Teachers get involved in :
1	prepare lesson plan before starting the teaching and learning session according to the student's current level
2	provide teaching aids before starting the teaching and learning session according to the students' current level
3	manage Teaching and learning according to the set timetable
4	provide teaching reflection after the end of the teaching and learning session
5	prepare a set of test/exam questions according to the current exam calendar
6	prepare a set of test/exam schemes according to the current examination calendar according to the level that has been determined
7	prepare test/exam sessions according to the time in the exam calendar and current exam instructions
8	mark the exam answers according to the scheme provided
9	key-in the exam scores for analysis and record purposes
10	planning matters related to the operation of student affairs at school
11	managing matters related to the operation of student affairs at the school
12	identify and resolve issues related to student welfare at school
13	supervise the special rooms of student affairs in the school according to the set portfolio
14	managing activities that increase the school's level of achievement in the fields of cheerfulness, hygiene, health and safety according to the set portfolio
15	documenting student affairs activities at school according to the set portfolio
16	plan extracurricular activities according to the school calendar given
17	carry out co-curricular activities according to the school calendar according to the given school calendar
18	planning activities that increase the level of school achievement in the extracurricular field
19	supervise the special rooms of the school curriculum
20	documenting school extracurricular activities
21	attend a professional development program related to co-curriculum
22	attend a continuous professional development program (CPD) to improve work competence

- 23 record the presence of co-curricular professionalism development programs in the SPLKPM System
- 24 master the skills of creating the latest educational technology and innovation
- 25 master the skills of developing the latest educational technology and innovation
- 26 master the skills of applying the latest educational technology and innovation
- 27 master the latest educational digital literacy skills
- 28 master the handling of the latest educational digital teaching aids
- 29 master the culture of online working
- 30 improve teamwork skills in school
- 31 improve problem-solving skills involving tasks at school
- 32 improve decision-making skills involving tasks at school
- 33 improve critical thinking skills in developing self-capacity at school
- 34 rest after finishing in managing things related to work at school
- 35 engage in sport activities to maintain personal fitness
- 36 perform worship activities according to their respective religious beliefs
- 39 socialize with the communities where they live
- 38 managing the household with their partner at home
- 39 managing children's education with spouse at home

Table 4 shows the findings of the study which consists of the threshold value of each element (d items), the threshold value of the construct (d construct) and the position of the item in question based on expert agreement.

Table 4. Threshold Value (d), Percentage of Expert Agreement, Defuzzification and Item Ranking for Elements of Engagement Balance

Results	Item1	Item2	Item3	Item4	Item5	Item6	Item7	Item8	Item9	Item10	Item11	Item12	Item13	Item14	Item15	Item16	Item17	Item18	Item19	Item20
Expert1	0.08981	0.08981	0.06415	0.0834	0.04491	0.04491	0.05132	0.05132	0.03208	0.05132	0.05132	0.06415	0.09623	0.09623	0.10264	0.17321	0.0834	0.18604	0.14755	0.17321
Expert2	0.08981	0.08981	0.06415	0.02566	0.04491	0.04491	0.00642	0.05132	0.03208	0.12189	0.12189	0.06415	0.09623	0.09623	0.04491	0.11547	0.0834	0.10264	0.14113	0.11547
Expert3	0.03208	0.03208	0.00642	0.02566	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.00642	0.02566	0.05132	0.05132	0.05132	0.07698	0.07698	0.07057	0.05774	0.08981	0.04491	0.03208	0.05774
Expert4	0.08981	0.08981	0.06415	0.0834	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.12189	0.03208	0.06415	0.06415	0.06415	0.03849	0.03849	0.04491	0.05774	0.02566	0.04491	0.0834	0.05774
Expert5	0.0834	0.0834	0.00642	0.02566	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.05132	0.03208	0.05132	0.05132	0.05132	0.07698	0.07698	0.07057	0.05774	0.08981	0.07057	0.03208	0.05774
Expert6	0.0834	0.03208	0.00642	0.02566	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.00642	0.02566	0.06415	0.06415	0.06415	0.03849	0.03849	0.04491	0.05774	0.02566	0.04491	0.0834	0.05774
Expert7	0.03208	0.0834	0.00642	0.08981	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.12189	0.14113	0.05132	0.05132	0.05132	0.03849	0.03849	0.04491	0.05774	0.08981	0.07057	0.03208	0.05774
Expert8	0.19887	0.19887	0.22453	0.20528	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.05132	0.03208	0.16679	0.16679	0.16679	0.19245	0.19245	0.18604	0.05774	0.02566	0.04491	0.14755	0.05774
Expert9	0.03208	0.03208	0.00642	0.02566	0.01283	0.01283	0.00642	0.05132	0.03208	0.12189	0.12189	0.06415	0.03849	0.03849	0.04491	0.05774	0.02566	0.04491	0.0834	0.05774
Statistics	Item1	Item2	Item3	Item4	Item5	Item6	Item7	Item8	Item9	Item10	Item11	Item12	Item13	Item14	Item15	Item16	Item17	Item18	Item19	Item20
Value of the item	0.08126	0.08126	0.0499	0.06558	0.01996	0.01996	0.01141	0.05702	0.04277	0.08268	0.08268	0.07128	0.07698	0.07698	0.07271	0.07698	0.05987	0.07271	0.08696	0.07698
Value of the construct																				
Item < 0.2	9	9	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
% of item < 0.2	100%	100%	88%	88%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Average of % consensus																				
Defuzzification	0.84444	0.84444	0.88889	0.85556	0.92222	0.92222	0.91111	0.91111	0.94444	0.78889	0.78889	0.78889	0.83333	0.83333	0.82222	0.8	0.85556	0.82222	0.75556	0.8
Ranking	7	7	4	6	2	2	3	3	1	11	11	11	8	8	9	10	6	9	12	10
Status	Accept																			

Results	Item21	Item22	Item23	Item24	Item25	Item26	Item27	Item28	Item29	Item30	Item31	Item32	Item33	Item34	Item35	Item36	Item37	Item38	Item39
Expert1	0.28226	0.04491	0.31434	0.10264	0.10264	0.08981	0.0834	0.07057	0.11547	0.10264	0.06415	0.07057	0.08981	0.19887	0.0834	0.03208	0.08981	0.05132	0.05132
Expert2	0.12189	0.04491	0.08981	0.10264	0.10264	0.08981	0.0834	0.01283	0.11547	0.10264	0.00642	0.01283	0.08981	0.08981	0.0834	0.03208	0.03208	0.05132	0.05132
Expert3	0.05132	0.01283	0.03208	0.07057	0.07057	0.0834	0.08981	0.01283	0.28868	0.18604	0.00642	0.01283	0.0834	0.0834	0.02566	0.03208	0.0834	0.00642	0.00642
Expert4	0.05132	0.01283	0.03208	0.04491	0.04491	0.03208	0.0834	0.01283	0.11547	0.10264	0.06415	0.07057	0.08981	0.08981	0.0834	0.03208	0.08981	0.05132	0.05132
Expert5	0.06415	0.01283	0.03208	0.07057	0.07057	0.0834	0.08981	0.10264	0.05774	0.07057	0.10906	0.10264	0.0834	0.0834	0.08981	0.14113	0.0834	0.12189	0.12189
Expert6	0.06415	0.01283	0.03208	0.04491	0.04491	0.03208	0.02566	0.01283	0.17321	0.10264	0.00642	0.01283	0.03208	0.03208	0.02566	0.02566	0.03208	0.00642	0.00642
Expert7	0.05132	0.01283	0.03208	0.07057	0.07057	0.0834	0.08981	0.10264	0.05774	0.07057	0.10906	0.10264	0.0834	0.03208	0.02566	0.02566	0.0834	0.12189	0.12189
Expert8	0.12189	0.01283	0.03208	0.18604	0.18604	0.0834	0.08981	0.01283	0.11547	0.18604	0.00642	0.01283	0.0834	0.03208	0.32075	0.03208	0.0834	0.05132	0.05132
Expert9	0.06415	0.01283	0.03208	0.10264	0.10264	0.08981	0.0834	0.07057	0.11547	0.10264	0.06415	0.01283	0.03208	0.08981	0.0834	0.03208	0.08981	0.05132	0.05132
Statistics	Item21	Item22	Item23	Item24	Item25	Item26	Item27	Item28	Item29	Item30	Item31	Item32	Item33	Item34	Item35	Item36	Item37	Item38	Item39
Value of the item	0.09694	0.01996	0.06986	0.08839	0.08839	0.07413	0.07983	0.04562	0.1283	0.11405	0.04847	0.04562	0.07413	0.08126	0.09124	0.04277	0.07413	0.05702	0.05702
Value of the construct																			
Item < 0.2	8	9	8	9	9	9	9	9	8	9	9	9	9	9	8	9	9	9	9
% of item < 0.2	88%	100%	88%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	88%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	88%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Average of % consensus																			98
Defuzzification	0.78889	0.92222	0.84444	0.82222	0.82222	0.84444	0.85556	0.87778	0.8	0.82222	0.88889	0.87778	0.84444	0.84444	0.85556	0.94444	0.84444	0.91111	0.91111
Ranking	11	2	7	9	7	6	5	10	9	4	5	7	7	7	6	1	7	3	3
Status	Accept																		

Expert agreement for all items of the engagement balance element has shown good value through the analysis explained above. Table 4 shows that there are four threshold values that have been blacked out because they

exceed the threshold value of 0.2 (>0.2). Threshold values that are blacked out indicate that there are different expert opinions at the same time as not reaching a consensus on a certain item. Despite this, the average value of all items in the time balance element shows a threshold value (d) <0.2 which is 0.06777. Chuan, Hsu & Chang (2011) stated that if the average threshold value (d) is found to be less than 0.2, the entire item has reached good agreement. All experts reached a consensus for all items in the balance element of engagement through the findings of the study. The overall percentage of expert agreement amounts to 98 percent. The percentage has shown that all items in the element of balance of engagement have met the conditions of expert agreement, which is a percentage of more than 75 percent. The findings of the study also show that all Alpha-Cut defuzzication values (average of fuzzy response) exceed α -cut = 0.5 and if less than that, then the item should be dropped. In conclusion, the items in the element of balance of involvement have been agreed upon by all the experts in the assessment. The items that have been agreed upon through expert consensus are arranged according to priority (ranking) as shown in Table 5 below :

Table 5: Position of the Items for the Elements of Engagement Balance

Number of items	ELEMENTS OF ENGAGEMENT BALANCE Teachers get involved in :	Experts agreement in percentage (%)	Experts agreement	Ranking
1	prepare lesson plan before starting the teaching and learning session according to the student's current level	100	Accept	7
2	provide teaching aids before starting the teaching and learning session according to the students' current level	100	Accept	7
3	manage teaching and learning according to the set timetable	88	Accept	4
4	provide teaching reflection after the end of the teaching and learning session	88	Accept	6
5	prepare a set of test/exam questions according to the current exam calendar	100	Accept	2
6	prepare a set of test/exam schemes according to the current examination calendar according to the level that has been determined	100	Accept	2
7	prepare test/exam sessions according to the time in the exam calendar and current exam instructions	100	Accept	3
8	mark the exam answers according to the scheme provided	100	Accept	3
9	key-in the exam scores for analysis and record purposes	100	Accept	1
10	planning matters related to the operation of student affairs at school	100	Accept	11
11	managing matters related to the operation of student affairs at the school	100	Accept	11
12	identify and resolve issues related to student welfare at school	100	Accept	11
13	supervise the special rooms of student affairs in the school according to the set portfolio	100	Accept	8
14	managing activities that increase the school's level of achievement in the fields of cheerfulness, hygiene, health and safety according to the set portfolio	100	Accept	8

15	documenting student affairs activities at school according to the set portfolio	100	Accept	9
16	plan extracurricular activities according to the school calendar given	100	Accept	10
17	carry out co-curricular activities according to the school calendar according to the given school calendar	100	Accept	6
18	planning activities that increase the level of school achievement in the extracurricular field	100	Accept	9
19	supervise the special rooms of the school curriculum	100	Accept	12
20	documenting school extracurricular activities	100	Accept	10
21	attend a professional development program related to co-curriculum	88	Accept	11
22	attend a continuous professional development program (CPD) to improve work competence	100	Accept	2
23	record the presence of co-curricular professionalism development programs in the SPLKPM System	88	Accept	7
24	master the skills of creating the latest educational technology and innovation	100	Accept	9
25	master the skills of developing the latest educational technology and innovation	100	Accept	9
26	master the skills of applying the latest educational technology and innovation	100	Accept	7
27	master the latest educational digital literacy skills	100	Accept	6
28	master the handling of the latest educational digital teaching aids	100	Accept	5
29	master the culture of online working	100	Accept	10
30	improve teamwork skills in school	100	Accept	9
31	improve problem-solving skills involving tasks at school	100	Accept	4
32	improve decision-making skills involving tasks at school	100	Accept	5
33	improve critical thinking skills in developing self-capacity at school	100	Accept	7
34	rest after finishing in managing things related to work at school	100	Accept	7
35	engage in sport activities to maintain personal fitness	88	Accept	6
36	perform worship activities according to their respective religious beliefs	100	Accept	1
37	socialize with the communities where they live	100	Accept	7
38	managing the household with their partner at home	100	Accept	3
39	managing children's education with spouse at home	100	Accept	3

After all the elements of the engagement balance have been agreed upon by the experts, a list according to priority that determines the highest priority to the lowest priority is generated based on Table 6 below :

Table 6. Position of the Elements of Engagement Balance Based on Priority

Arrangement sort by priority	ELEMENTS OF ENGAGEMENT BALANCE Teachers get involved in :	Previous item number
1	key-in the exam scores for analysis and record purposes	9
	perform worship activities according to their respective religious beliefs	36
2	prepare a set of test/exam questions according to the current exam calendar	5
	prepare a set of test/exam schemes according to the current examination calendar according to the level that has been determined	6
	attend a continuous professional development program (CPD) to improve work competence	22
3	prepare test/exam sessions according to the time in the exam calendar and current exam instructions	7
	mark the exam answers according to the scheme provided	8
	managing the household with their partner at home	38
	managing children's education with spouse at home	39
4	manage Teaching and learning according to the set timetable	3
	improve problem-solving skills involving tasks at school	31
5	master the handling of the latest educational digital teaching aids	28
	improve decision-making skills involving tasks at school	32
6	provide teaching reflection after the end of the teaching and learning session	4
	carry out co-curricular activities according to the school calendar according to the given school calendar	17
	master the latest educational digital literacy skills	27
	engage in sport activities to maintain personal fitness	35
7	prepare lesson plan before starting the teaching and learning session according to the student's current level	1
	provide teaching aids before starting the teaching and learning session according to the students' current level	2
	record the presence of co-curricular professionalism development programs in the SPLKPM System	23
	master the skills of applying the latest educational technology and innovation	26
	improve critical thinking skills in developing self-capacity at school	33
	rest after finishing in managing things related to work at school	34
	socialize with the communities where they live	37
8	supervise the special rooms of student affairs in the school according to the set portfolio	13
	managing activities that increase the school's level of achievement in the fields of cheerfulness, hygiene, health and safety according to the set portfolio	14
9	documenting student affairs activities at school according to the set portfolio	15
	planning activities that increase the level of school achievement in the extracurricular field	18
	master the skills of creating the latest educational technology and innovation	24
	master the skills of developing the latest educational technology and innovation	25
	improve teamwork skills in school	30
10	plan extracurricular activities according to the school calendar given	16

	documenting school extracurricular activities	20
	master the culture of online working	29
11	planning matters related to the operation of student affairs at school	10
	managing matters related to the operation of student affairs at the school	11
	identify and resolve issues related to student welfare at school	12
	attend a professional development program related to co-curriculum	21
12	supervise the special rooms of the school curriculum	19

Based on the order of priority that has been agreed upon by experts, items are found that *Teachers get involved in key-in the exam scores for analysis and record purposes* and *Teachers get involved in perform worship activities according to their respective religious beliefs* occupies the top priority list. The results of this finding show the teachers' concern in placing religious appreciation as the most important item in the priority list of the most important level for the element of engagement balance. The findings of this study are significant with Putra's (2020) study which states that religious factors are at the core of the six main aspects of the observational analysis of his study. The results of Garg's study (2017) are also synonymous with the findings of the study which states that spiritual elements in the workplace are recommended as an important medium to improve work life balance and employee well-being. Anupama et al., (2021) also identified that spiritual factors in the workplace positively affect the work life balance of professionals. Apart from that, research findings from Gallup (2010) stated that there is a relationship between religiosity and employee engagement. In fact, research findings by Ma'ruf (2019) assert that the balance of human life is balancing physical and spiritual needs or in other words the interests of this world and the hereafter. After all, religious appreciation is the most important entity in the top ranking element of engagement balance which is the mainstay of the work-life balance of secondary school teachers in Malaysia.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The management of a teacher's work-life balance is an important matter in producing teachers who are balanced in physical and spiritual needs. Based on the findings of the study and discussion have shown the importance of the balance element of involvement in the management of the work life balance of secondary school teachers in Malaysia. The agreement and prioritization of items by experts is expected to generate a balance of teacher involvement from a psychological point of view and their commitment. The results of this study can contribute towards the application of work-life balance management in career and outside of work hours. The researcher suggested that the same study be extended to school support staff to see the expert's view on the need for elements of work-life balance that are required.

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